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Background

The Accelerated Testing Methodology (ATM) can be used for the prediction of the long-term life of CFRP.

The tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP is important and fundamental data for the reliable design of CFRP structures.

Recently, thermoplastic epoxy resin (TPEP) has been developed and used for CFRP structures.

Objective

In this study, the statistical life of TPEP resin impregnated carbon fiber strand (CFRTP strand) under creep tension loading was evaluated under dry and wet conditions using the ATM we developed.

Formulation of statistical creep strength

Static strength

$$\log \sigma_s(t, T) = \log \sigma_0(t_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_s(t, T)}{E_s(t_0, T_0)} \right]$$

Creep strength

$$\log \sigma_c(t, T) = \log \sigma_0(t_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_c(t, T)}{E_c(t_0, T_0)} \right]$$

$$E_c(t, T) = E_s(At, T) = E_r(At/2, T)$$

$$\log A = \log(1 + 1/k_R)$$

t : Failure time
 t_0 : Reference time
 T : Temperature
 T_0 : Reference temperature
 P_f : Failure probability
 σ_0 and α : Scale and shape parameters of static strength at t_0 and T_0
 n_R : Viscoelastic parameter determined by failure mode
 E_s : Viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin under static tensile
 E_c : Viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin under constant loading

Testing method

Test material

CFRTP strand	Carbon fiber	Resin
T700/TPEP	T700SC-6000	Thermoplastic epoxy (TPEP)
T300/TPEP	T300-3000	

Viscoelastic test for matrix resin

Static strength test for CFRTP strands

E_r : Relaxation modulus of matrix resin

σ_0 : Scale parameters of static strength at t_0 and T_0

α : Shape parameters of static strength at t_0 and T_0

n_R : Viscoelastic parameter determined by failure mode

Results and Discussion

Relaxation modulus of matrix resin

Static tensile strength of CFRTP strand

Weibull distribution of static tensile strength for CFRTP strand

Static tensile strength of CFRTP strand versus viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin

Parameters in formulation

		σ_0 [MPa]	α [-]	n_R [-]
T700/TPEP	Dry	4,970	15	0.102
	Wet	4,710	23	0.167
T300/TPEP	Dry	3,600	16	0.060
	Wet	3,570	20	0.127

Comparison of predictions and experiments

Long-term creep life prediction at reference temperature of 25°C

Conclusion

- Statistical creep strength of unidirectional CFRTP under tensile loading in the fiber direction can be predicted using ATM not only in dry but also in wet conditions.
- There is no difference in creep strength reduction with time and temperature for two kinds of unidirectional CFRTP.
- This reduction in creep strength is accelerated by water absorption.

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